

PROJECT-BASED APPROACH AND ESSENTIAL LEARNING COMPETENCIES IN FOOD AND BEVERAGE SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to find out the teaching approach essential in learning competencies in Food and Beverage Services on selected Senior High School students for the school year 2020 to 2021 in the Division of Quezon. Specifically, it sought to identify the teaching approach and essential learning competencies in Food and Beverage Services from the utilization of project-based approach through focus group discussions, determine any significant difference in the pretest and posttest scores of the respondents and evaluate after the use of the approach. Using mixed method design, the study was conducted in at Lina Gayeta Lasquety National High School in District of Padre Burgos, Quezon. It was revealed that there are 4 positive points revealed in the identification of teaching approach as the central theme points out in highlighting its dynamics. There are six essential learning competencies in Food and Beverage Services. The students demonstrate better performance after using the project-based approach. The project-based approach is also very highly observable in terms of scope, sequence, integration and articulation. In the light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher gave this general recommendation that project-based approach using essential competencies may be adopted and may be subjected to further research for its effectiveness. The respondents in nature are young and open for new learning and experiences, other educational authorities may evaluate such as teachers and school heads Additional activities for improvement of the approach to make it highly effective among the students so that, it will provide more opportunities for them to learn other competencies.

Keywords: Project-based, Food and Beverage Services, learning competencies